

QPing: a Quantum Ping Primitive for Quantum Networks

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Abstract—We introduce the concept of **Quantum Ping (QPing)** as a diagnostic primitive for future quantum networks, designed to assess whether two or more end nodes can establish practical quantum entanglement under given resource and time constraints, with controlled overhead and time-adaptive fidelity thresholds. Unlike classical ping, which probes network-layer connectivity through ICMP messages, our proposed quantum version is adapted to the unique features of quantum networks, where connectivity depends on the availability and quality of shared entanglement. We develop a formal framework for QPing and leverage tools such as sequential hypothesis testing to probe quantum connectivity. We present several strategies, including active strategies with path-based and segment-based variants, and resource-based strategies that utilize pre-shared entangled resources. We further provide a quantitative performance evaluation of these strategies, including diagnostic cost, latency, and feasibility under time-dependent decoherence.

QPing can serve as a flexible diagnostic building block for quantum networks, designed to operate alongside fundamental network operations and to accommodate different architectural assumptions and protocol design approaches.

Index Terms—Entanglement, Quantum Networks, Quantum Communication, Quantum Routing, Quantum State Verification, Fidelity Witnessing

I. INTRODUCTION

Quantum networks promise to introduce a new paradigm in communication, enabling unique and powerful applications such as distributed sensing [1]–[5], quantum cryptography [6], [7], and distributed quantum computation [8]–[10], among others [11]. These capabilities are expected to come together in a comprehensive, large-scale quantum network, linking users and cities, and ultimately giving rise to the Quantum Internet [12]–[17].

Significant efforts have been dedicated to analyzing both the fundamental and advanced components required for a quantum network [18]–[20]. These studies encompass hierarchical stack models [21]–[23] that structure network entities into distinct layers, facilitating modular development and clearer functionality. Key devices within these networks include quantum repeaters [24]–[28], which extend communication ranges by overcoming quantum signal degradation, but also elements as routers [29]–[32] designed to manage efficient state connectivity across the network. Protocols such as those for entanglement distribution and manipulation [33]–[37] are critical for establishing and maintaining quantum entanglement between network nodes. Many of these entities exhibit parallels to the

classical Internet functionalities, but are specifically tailored to address the unique challenges of quantum communication.

In this work, we consider a fundamental component of the classical Internet architecture, namely, the ping program [38], [39], which currently lacks a direct counterpart in quantum networks. In classical computer networks, the ping program serves as a straightforward tool to inquire about network-layer connectivity, enabling testing of node reachability and providing information on the latency involved.

Unfortunately, classical ping strategies are unable to fully test connectivity in quantum networks, which differs profoundly from classical network-layer connectivity due to entanglement. In quantum networks, connectivity arises from shared entangled states and is enabled by the capability to establish entangled links between two nodes, with the “quality” of these links related to the fidelity and robustness of the entanglement.

To address this gap, we introduce the concept of *Quantum Ping (QPing)*, a tool designed to verify both the existence and the quality of entanglement links within a quantum network. Specifically, we design quantum primitives that form the foundation of diagnostic protocols, which can be deployed within different functionalities for the Quantum Internet [21]–[23]. Indeed, tools that test entanglement-based connectivity are complementary to functionalities such as path selection, resource allocation, and quantum-specific foreseen Quality of Service (QoS) assessment for application requirements.

Our proposal is motivated not only by theoretical considerations but also by the growing need for scalable real-time diagnostics in emerging quantum network architectures [16], [40]. We define several strategies for realizing the quantum ping, reflecting distinct operational and architectural assumptions. Active strategies aim to verify whether entanglement distribution can produce a useful entangled link, while resource-based strategies are designed to probe an entangled link from previously shared states. In each case, we make use of tools for entanglement verification such as sequential hypothesis testing [41]–[45], fidelity witnessing [46], or Bell-type inequalities [47], and we analyze how time enters as a resource-limiting factor in the active cases.

Time plays an important role not only in the execution of the protocol, but also in determining the required thresholds for entanglement quality. As quantum states degrade over time due to decoherence and operational errors, both the process

of actively establishing remote entanglement and the quality thresholds themselves are affected. In addition, to assess the quality of entanglement, measurements are necessary, which in turn destroy part of the entangled quantum states. That is, the quality of a quantum connection cannot simply be assessed, but requires consuming some of the resources one actually would like to establish and use. While this is unavoidable, one clearly would like to minimize the required overheads.

Our approaches seek to optimize performance by avoiding resource-intensive methods such as quantum process tomography [48], [49], which can be inefficient and provide excessive information beyond what is necessary. While both classical and quantum ping ultimately aim to answer a binary question, the quantum counterpart is far more challenging to resolve. In classical networks, the query is simply to check node-host reachability. In quantum networks, the question becomes whether the fidelity of the shared entanglement exceeds a (possibly time-dependent) threshold, a yes/no decision that is harder to answer because fidelity can degrade over time due to decoherence and operational errors. Moreover, quantum measurements often reveal more information than is strictly necessary to determine this binary outcome, making it difficult to design tests that are both resource-efficient and minimally invasive. This challenge is particularly relevant when assessing the feasibility of entanglement purification or distillation.

The paper is structured as follows. In Sec. II, we review some basic concepts and related literature. In Sec. III, we properly define the concept of quantum ping and its underlying design framework. Furthermore, we introduce our system model by detailing the quantities of interest. In Sec. IV, we present different QPing strategies able to probe quantum connectivity in different network settings. Then, the Qping performance evaluation is discussed in Sec. V, where we evaluate some key performance metrics, such as the expected number of diagnostic trials, acceptance probability and expected time to decision. Finally, we summarize our proposal and provide insights on further extensions of this work in Sec. VI.

II. BACKGROUND

In this section, we briefly review some basic concepts and tools we make use of throughout this work, and we better substantiate the context of the quantum equivalent of ping. To this aim, it is useful to recall the main features of the classical ping program and its role in the classical Internet architecture.

A. Classical Ping

The classical ping utility is a fundamental tool in computer networks used to verify the reachability of a remote host through Internet Control Message Protocol (ICMP) messages [50]. In classical systems, the ICMP is used for error reporting and allows for assessing the nature of errors that occur at the network layer. The ping program sends ICMP messages to verify whether a destination is responsive. Its operation is very simple: a host sends an ICMP Echo Request to the IP address identifying the destination, and if no errors occur, that is, the

network layer can successfully reach the destination, the node responds with an ICMP Echo reply [38], [39]. This operation provides feedback about the network layer connectivity by testing the routing information [38], [39]. Indeed, from the Echo reply, one can assert that the destination was reachable and evaluate an approximate round-trip time, giving a basic measure of latency. As is known, the rationale behind the ping program stems from the best-effort nature of the network layer, which provides no guarantees regarding the ability to find a path to a destination. Clearly, the ping program does not guarantee reliable network layer services. In contrast, it tests network-layer connectivity by actively transmitting a packet, which triggers network-layer functionalities, thus testing the routing service.

As a consequence, despite its simplicity, the ping program plays an essential role in real-time diagnostics, precisely because of its simple nature and binary outcome, i.e., “host reachable or not”. In this work, we explore how a conceptually analogous strategy could be defined in quantum networks, where connectivity involves fundamentally different resources and constraints.

B. Quantum Network Connectivity

As mentioned above, in quantum networks, connectivity is no longer defined by the presence of a classical communication channel, but by the ability to establish quantum entanglement between two or more nodes. This quantum connectivity may be achieved either dynamically, by generating and distributing entangled states [51], or through local manipulation from pre-established resource states [21]. However, several communication constraints arise, such as the impossibility of cloning unknown quantum information [52]. Additionally, decoherence imposes temporal constraints, making quantum connectivity vanish over time, and the imperfect operations required to establish entangled links degrade the entangled resource. Given such constraints, it is essential to evaluate the *quality* of entangled links through meaningful metrics to discern *practically useful* quantum connections. In this regard, several quantities may be considered, including the time required to establish the quantum connection, the noise model and its impact.

In this paper, we refer to quantum connection quality as the similarity between the entangled links –entangled states shared between qubits held at remote nodes– and the expected noiseless entangled state. More in detail, we consider fidelity serving as the primary metric and then further develop the tests and the quality metric according to different settings and QPing strategies. This allows us to provide a comprehensive set of tools able to genuinely test quantum network connectivity for different network design architectures, as better described in the following.

C. Network Architectures and Functionalities

Quantum network architecture has been studied extensively, with several proposals aiming to organize their complex functionalities into layered stack models [21]–[23]. These

models typically include physical layer handling hardware and quantum memories, link layer responsible for entanglement distribution and purification, and network layer tasked with routing and resource management. However, the different proposed design approaches vary in their perspective and the design philosophy, ranging from bottom-up approaches [53]–[56] to top-down schemes [18], [21], [33], [36], [57]. The former typically exploits the underlying physical topology of the network and aims to build entanglement connections along it. In contrast, top-down approaches circumvent physical constraints by leveraging pre-shared entanglement to create tailored topologies on demand. These entanglement-based designs enable the dynamic construction of logical links through local operations and measurements.

At the core of these architectures are entanglement distribution protocols [33], [34], [36], [37], [58]–[61]. They include methods such as direct entanglement generation over physical channels, entanglement swapping via intermediate nodes (repeaters), and entanglement purification to enhance fidelity [24]–[26]. Efficient distribution is challenged by loss, noise, and memory coherence times, making reliable entanglement generation and distribution a non-trivial engineering task.

A subsequent key functionality is entanglement routing, which addresses the problem of identifying optimal paths through a network to establish entanglement between distant nodes [30]–[32]. Routing protocols must balance factors like path fidelity, resource availability, and latency, also relying on classical signaling.

Quantum ping protocols should be designed to suit the requirements and structural features of each network architecture approach. To this end, we present a general formulation of tests and quality metrics that can be applied across different architectures. While the formulation does not require a detailed knowledge of the specific entanglement distribution or routing mechanisms, it assumes that the core functionalities for entanglement generation, distribution, and routing are available and can serve the quantum ping operation.

Specifically, in its active variants, the quantum ping strategies trigger generation and distribution of entanglement over a candidate path, implicitly testing both connectivity and management. Furthermore, the segment-based variant allows to test multiple individual links in batch, providing information on single-hop quantum connectivity. Finally, the resource-based strategy leverages pre-shared entangled resources and exploits functionalities such as routing based on resource state and entanglement control to extract an entangled state through local operations.

In conclusion, the proposed QPing strategies inherently exploit entanglement generation and distribution, as well as entanglement-aware routing. Consequently, a successful QPing execution implicitly verifies the correctness, consistency, and availability of the underlying routing data. In particular, active QPing strategies directly test routing information by confirming the physical availability and viability of the selected entanglement distribution path. In contrast, resource-based QPing approaches validate the extracted quantum link, ensuring that

routing strategy that locally manipulates the entanglement resources indeed match the desired topology.

QPing is not a link-layer protocol and does not aim to establish or maintain entanglement between neighboring nodes. In contrast to quantum link-layer designs, which broadly address distribution strategies, scheduling, and reliable entanglement delivery at the hop level, QPing operates as a diagnostic primitive that probes the feasibility of end-to-end quantum connectivity under time-dependent constraints. Its purpose is to inform higher-layer decisions such as whether to attempt routing, entanglement distillation, or application protocols, rather than to manage entanglement generation itself.

Similarly, QPing is not a routing protocol and does not perform path selection or resource allocation. Instead, it acts as a diagnostic primitive that can be invoked by routing or control-plane mechanisms to evaluate the feasibility of candidate paths under time-dependent conditions. By providing early accept, reject, or abort decisions, QPing enables routing algorithms to avoid attempting entanglement distribution on paths that are unlikely to meet service requirements, thereby reducing unnecessary resource consumption. In this sense, QPing plays a role analogous to classical ping, which complements but does not replace link-layer or transport-layer protocols.

To the best of our knowledge, such a concrete formulation of a quantum ping primitive has not been addressed so far.

III. QUANTUM PING DESIGN

A. Design Objectives

Given the above discussion, a quantum ping test for quantum connectivity should answer the question “Is there usable entanglement?”, where usable entanglement refers to entangled states that pass a specified quality criterion. The design of quantum ping strategies is operatively translated into the definition of such a quality criterion and its test. Towards this design, we aim to preserve the features that make the classical ping effective, namely, lightweight network resource consumption and simplicity. Notably, these two features are particularly challenging to achieve in the context of quantum networks. Indeed, to observe the quality of an entangled state, this should be measured and hence consumed.

In this regard, the strategies for quantum state reconstruction such as quantum state tomography and quantum process tomography, which respectively characterize quantum states and quantum channels, are heavily resource-consuming and difficult to scale as the number of parameters to be determined exponentially increases with the dimension of the space of the system [48], [49]. As a consequence, although tomography allows for the characterization of an entangled link, it is not a viable strategy due to complexity and resource overhead.

To mirror the simple nature of classical ping, we avoid tomography and aim to design minimal tests for quantum connectivity under temporal and hardware limits: finite memory and imperfect operations constrain purification attempts and maximum fidelity. Consequently, the possibility of entanglement purification and fidelity thresholds depends on each

setting capabilities, so QPing procedures must be tailored to each scenario.

We remark that the goal of QPing is not to guarantee entanglement distribution under arbitrary noise conditions, but to assess the feasibility of establishing usable entanglement within given time and resource budgets. QPing is therefore most relevant in regimes where entanglement distribution is uncertain or costly, and where early abort decisions can avoid inefficient resource utilization. The numerical analyses provided in Sec. V are designed to probe this feasibility boundary rather than guaranteed-delivery performance.

B. System Model

We consider a quantum network consisting of nodes, connected by quantum channels, that is capable of distributing entanglement. Nodes may function as users, repeaters, or routers, and the network may operate under various considerations.

We explore different scenarios and possible definitions of a Quantum Ping, grounded in the unique characteristics of quantum networks. The overall underlying goal is to check whether a quantum connection can be established between two parties, that is, whether useful entanglement can be generated between them, and, in some cases, to witness its quality (see Fig. 1).

Specifically, given two quantum nodes and a quantum task or application T (e.g., purification, teleportation, QKD, secret sharing), we can formally define the minimal required fidelity.

Definition 1 (*Task-Specific Minimal required fidelity*). *Let A and B be two network nodes sharing a quantum connection ρ_{AB} and let T be a quantum task or application. The task-specific minimal required fidelity F_0^T for task T is the smallest fidelity such that T can be successfully performed. Formally:*

$$F(\rho_{AB}, |\Phi^+\rangle) = \langle \Phi^+ | \rho_{AB} | \Phi^+ \rangle \geq F_0^T, \quad (1)$$

where ρ_{AB} is a shared bipartite quantum state required to perform T , and $|\Phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$ is the reference Bell state.

Note that this definition can be extended to more general kinds of entangled, including multipartite or higher dimensional, states.

In Eq. 1, $F(\rho_{AB}, |\Phi^+\rangle)$ denotes the fidelity of the state ρ_{AB} with respect to the target Bell state, serving as quantitative measure of the quality of the shared quantum resource ρ_{AB} , while F_0^T denotes a task-specific threshold, i.e., the minimum fidelity value that must be satisfied in order for the quantum task or application T to be successfully executed. Different tasks may then impose different values of F_0^T , so the ping procedure is tailored to ensure $\Pr(F(\rho_{AB}, |\Phi^+\rangle) \geq F_0^T)$ exceeds some desired confidence level, specified according to the QPing strategy.

This formulation ensures that QPing answers the precise question: ‘‘Is there usable entanglement between A and B for application T under the given temporal and hardware limitations?’’ We recall that, in quantum networks, connectivity cannot be treated as a static property. The quality of shared

Fig. 1: General idea of Quantum Ping (QPing). Two nodes of the network aim to decide whether they can generate and share useful entanglement between them.

entanglement evolves over time due to decoherence, stochastic entanglement-generation delays, and imperfect operations. As a consequence, any diagnostic primitive must explicitly account for the temporal evolution of entanglement quality rather than assuming a time-invariant system.

With the above in mind, we can define the QPing diagnostic as follows.

Quantum Ping. *Given access to a quantum network, determine whether two nodes A and B can establish an entangled state ρ_{AB} such that $F(\rho_{AB}, |\Phi^+\rangle)(t) > F_0(t)$ with high confidence, and using minimal quantum resources.*

Observe how, in analogy with the classical ping, the time to establish a quantum connection should be incorporated as a central metric in the connectivity diagnostic. However, rather than referring to the runtime of the ping procedure itself, we focus on the expected time required to generate a usable quantum connection, that is, to successfully distribute entanglement with sufficient quality between two end-nodes. This time is not only an observable output of the diagnostic, but also a factor that influences the operational fidelity threshold tested by QPing $F_0(t)$, which determines whether the resulting entanglement is useful for further applications.

Specifically, while F_0^T (defined in Def. 1) is a logical requirement and states the task-specific minimum fidelity needed at the time of use for a given task T , the QPing threshold $F_0(t)$ is a time-variant operative threshold that accounts for the degradation of entanglement occurring between state generation and task execution.

The operational threshold $F_0(t)$ can be set accounting for the minimal required fidelity F_0^T and for fidelity degradation due to network operative conditions. As an illustrative example, let the task T be QKD with minimal fidelity requirement $F_0^{QKD} = 0.9$, and let us denote the initial fidelity with $F(t_0)$, that is, the fidelity of the state generated at time instant t_0 . If operational errors and memory decoherence during the process of establishing entanglement reduce the fidelity of 0.5 within 100 ns, then the state must be initially prepared with

$F(t_0) > 0.95$ to ensure it still satisfies $F(t_{\text{use}}) \geq F_0^{QKD}$ at the time of use, where $t_0 - t_{\text{use}} \leq 100 \text{ ns}$. Therefore, QPing strategies must internalize this time-to-use notion, rather than a simplistic “distribution time”, to remain compatible with the temporal and operational constraints of quantum hardware.

Different effects can affect the dynamical definition of $F_0(t)$, among which we can highlight:

- *Memory decoherence times.*— Note that the entanglement quality decays with memory decoherence time, generally speaking as $F_0(t) \approx F_0 \exp(-t/\tau)$ [62], [63]. Classical messaging and delays from classical processing would contribute to such decoherence.
- *Gate and operational errors.*— Entanglement swapping operation between not perfect states leads to lower fidelity resulting states [16], [64]. Imperfect implementations of swapping operations also accumulates noise, leading to reduced fidelities $F_0(t) \approx F_0 \exp(-t/\tau) q_{\text{gate}}^{N_{\text{gates}}}$.
- *Entanglement distribution times.*— Entanglement swapping operations may be non deterministic [24], [65], leading to stochastic distribution times that depend on the number of attempts required for success. In general, $F_0(t) \approx F_0 \exp(-t_{\text{dist}}/\tau)$, where t_{dist} is the average distribution time that depends on the attempt success probability, per trial $\approx 1/p$.

Note that these effects not only affect the operational fidelity threshold but also limit the maximum achievable fidelity. If, for instance, decoherence and gate errors reduce any initially prepared state below the application threshold within the usable time window, no protocol will succeed. Therefore, QPing must evaluate the initial fidelity threshold F_0 , i.e., the threshold fidelity value at generation time, *and* whether the network can realistically produce such a state under its operational constraints, intrinsic to the network hardware and architecture. We specifically consider these different operational features and how they affect the different protocols in the performance evaluation of Sec. V.

Diagnostic value vs. direct execution: The benefit of QPing can be interpreted through a simple decision-theoretic model. Let C_{ping} denote the expected cost of executing a QPing diagnostic, and C_{app} the resource cost of attempting a full application protocol (e.g., QKD or distributed computation) on a given route. If the prior probability that the route satisfies the application’s fidelity threshold is P_{good} , directly executing the application blindly consumes C_{app} , yielding an expected wasted cost of $(1 - P_{\text{good}}) C_{\text{app}}$ when the route is inadequate.

In contrast, a ping-first strategy incurs an expected cost of

$$E[C_{\text{ping-first}}] = C_{\text{ping}} + P_{\text{accept}} C_{\text{app}}, \quad (2)$$

where P_{accept} is the probability that QPing determines the route to be usable and allows the application to proceed. Assuming the diagnostic is accurate ($P_{\text{accept}} \approx P_{\text{good}}$), the ping-first strategy provides a net resource savings ($E[C_{\text{ping-first}}] < C_{\text{app}}$) whenever

$$C_{\text{ping}} < (1 - P_{\text{good}}) C_{\text{app}}, \quad (3)$$

i.e., whenever the diagnostic overhead is strictly less than the expected cost of failed application attempts. This regime corresponds precisely to the boundary region, where uncertainty is high and the early abort mechanism prevents the catastrophic waste of C_{app} (where typically $C_{\text{app}} \gg C_{\text{ping}}$).

IV. QUANTUM PING VERSIONS AND OPERATIONAL STRATEGIES

In the following, we detail the proposed strategies, which can be classified into active and resource-based diagnostic modes. In active diagnostic mode, we distinguish between QPing strategies aimed at evaluating an entire path (provided by the routing functionality) and those focused on testing individual segments, namely, fractions of a given path. Finally, we consider resource-based mode for testing entangled links obtained from a re-shared resource.

As we describe in the scenarios below, the evaluation of this operative threshold will differ depending on the diagnostic mode and strategy, whether based on segments, end-to-end connections, or pre-established resource states. We refer to Table I for a comprehensive summary and comparison between the strategies we introduce.

We note that the specific solutions presented here are intended as proof-of-concept examples. In practice, more sophisticated or alternative tools could be employed depending on the network architecture and application requirements.

Remark. Throughout this work, we refer to a QPing diagnostic mode as *active* when it explicitly triggers entanglement distribution processes across the network. Conversely, the QPing strategy in resource-based diagnostic mode operates on pre-established resources, such as those resulting from background distribution protocols already executed, entanglement reservoirs, or multipartite resource states [22], [66], [67].

This terminology differs from the conventional terminology in classical networking, where active routing refers to the dynamic computation of paths during data transmission, as opposed to session routing, where a route is fixed during virtual circuit setup and followed passively thereafter [68]. In both cases, classical routing decisions are concerned with the path, whereas in QPing, our distinction is orthogonal and focuses on whether the diagnostic process activates the entanglement generation and distribution process or probes existing entanglement. This distinction is subtle but crucial, as it accommodates both proactive and reactive entanglement routing paradigms, where routing decisions and entanglement distribution occur in varying orders [32].

From the perspective discussed in [32], QPing active strategies stimulate both internal and external phases of routing functionality, forcing the network to instantiate the logical route physically through entanglement distribution. Differently, resource-based strategies probe the existing state and prior routing decisions, intended as pre-selected entangled links and a sequence of Pauli measurements.

While the proposed QPing primitive is conceptually aligned with the output of the classical ping, its implementation and

operational semantics depart significantly due to the fundamental characteristics of quantum networks. Specifically, and as remarked, it is necessarily interleaved with key quantum network functionalities such as entanglement generation, distribution, routing, and management. As these functionalities do not have a direct mapping in the classical Internet protocol stack [23], and the design of abstract models for quantum networks is ongoing, we avoid the rigorous definition of diagnostic protocols for quantum networks. In light of this, the proposed QPing is not coupled to a specific protocol stack or architectural models. Differently, it can be conceived as a *functionality-driven* primitive, that is, a tool that relies on the availability of core functionalities (such as entanglement generation, distribution, manipulation) while abstracting from their specific structure and implementation. Note that this tool can be easily deployed within advanced quantum network architectures, where the QPing is leveraged as a service unit and complemented by rules, messages, and interfaces to form a rigorous diagnostic network protocol tailored to the architecture.

As a consequence, our proposal represents a layer-agnostic module that serves as a *primitive* for diagnostic protocols in quantum networks.

A. Path-based Active QPing

The first scenario is pictorially represented in Fig 2 and referred to as *path-based* active ping. This QPing version enables two end nodes to test whether a useful quantum link can be established through a given path, selected by the network routing process or, if the path computation has not been performed, computed by a path finding algorithm. In this scenario, the path-based QPing aims at answering the question “Is the fidelity of the entanglement that can be generated between these two nodes high enough to perform a certain task?”. More in detail, we aim to assess whether the fidelity of the entangled state distributed over the path exceeds the threshold fidelity. As discussed in Sec. III, this fidelity threshold will depend on factors such as the type of entanglement (e.g., bipartite or multipartite), decoherence, memory decay effects, and the operational noise (e.g., the quality of local gates). These variables define an operational threshold fidelity, $F_0(t)$, typically lower than the minimal fidelity required for the application F_0^T , and the problem ultimately reduces to a fidelity witnessing problem [46].

If the end nodes are capable of storing multiple entangled pairs and performing entanglement distillation prior to application, then the QPing diagnostic question becomes: “Is the fidelity of the entanglement that can be generated between these two nodes high enough to allow successful purification?” Importantly, the availability of entanglement distillation does not alter the structure of the QPing protocol itself, but rather only affects its operational parameters.

The fidelity witnessing problem consists in deciding whether the fidelity of a quantum state lies above or below a given threshold—typically framed as a hypothesis testing task—while incurring minimal overhead. In Ref. [46], we proposed

(a) Path-based active QPing protocol.

(b) Segment-based active QPing protocol.

Fig. 2: Active Quantum Ping strategies. (a) Path-based. A whole path between the end nodes is tested through end-node strategy, where measurements are performed at both end nodes, or bouncing strategy, where one qubit is bounced back through the path and global measurement is performed at one end node. (b) Segment based. The individual segments composing the path between the end nodes are simultaneously and individually tested.

different strategies to tackle this problem using only local operations. While not optimal, since they reveal slightly more information than strictly needed, they offer efficient solutions directly applicable to address the QPing problem.

In our proposal, we resort to sequential hypothesis testing [41]–[45], following and extending the strategies we proposed in Ref. [46], integrating both *end-node* and *bouncing* strategies. The proposed strategies gather only the essential information required to solve a binary problem with high probability and confidence, dynamically adapting the solution over time. This approach ensures efficient information collection while balancing accuracy and speed, with continuous adaptation to evolving data and time-dependent factors, making it ideal for real-time quantum systems.

In the context of QPing, however, one can consider a variant in which a Bell pair is prepared at one end, send one qubit through the path to the other node, and then send it back so that the original node holds both particles again. A single

joint (global) Bell-state measurement can then estimate the fidelity of the full round-trip. For this reason, this variant is also referred to as bouncing strategy. This uses fewer local operations but doubles the noise (each link is traversed twice). While resource-saving, the double passage can importantly reduce fidelity and even break entanglement; hence, one must carefully adjust the threshold to account for this. In practice, this bouncing strategy might be useful for quicker checks or for individual segment testing (see below), but it carries the risk of misleading results if the path is very noisy.

In the following, we summarize the two variants of the path-based active QPing with a step-by-step description, which includes dynamical time evaluation and is based on statistical decisions (see also Fig. 2).

1) *Active End-node Strategy:*

- (i) *Path assumption.*– Given a path between two end nodes, choose a prior distribution $P(F(t))$ over fidelity values, reflecting prior path knowledge. If no such knowledge exists, a uniform distribution may be assumed.
- (ii) *Collect data.*– Establish entangled states between end nodes and perform local measurements of random Pauli correlations [46]. After n trials, let k be the number of “passes” observed at time t . By Hoeffding/Chernoff-type bounds, the frequency k/n concentrates around its expectation, providing statistical confidence [46]. This process reveals the pass/fail counts needed for fidelity witnessing. One can tune and actively update the protocol efficiency as follows.
- (iii) *Statistical update.*– Compute the posterior distribution $P(F | \text{data})$ using Bayes theorem:

$$P(F(t) | k, n) = \frac{P(k | F(t), n) \cdot P(F(t))}{\int_0^1 P(k | F(t), n) \cdot P(F(t)) dF}, \quad (4)$$

where $P(F(t))$ models the probability of a “pass” given fidelity $F(t)$.

- (iv) *Compute Posterior Probability.*– Evaluate:

$$P(F(t) \geq F_0(t) | \text{data}) = \int_{F_0(t)}^1 P(F(t) | \text{data}) dF. \quad (5)$$

- (v) *Decision rule (hypothesis test).*– Choose a confidence threshold $\eta \in [0, 1]$, and an uncertainty parameter δ . Then:

- If $P(F(t) \geq F_0(t) | \text{data}) \geq \eta$, “accept” the link (ping success). Otherwise “reject” the link (ping fail).
- Optionally: if $P(F(t) \geq F_0(t)) \in [\eta - \delta, \eta + \delta]$, declare “inconclusive”.

QPing is implemented as a Bayesian sequential hypothesis test. After each diagnostic trial, the posterior distribution over the relevant fidelity parameter is updated, and a decision is taken when the posterior tail probability exceeds a confidence threshold. At each step, time advances (more pairs are tested), and the posterior probability distribution is updated adaptively. This sequential procedure naturally balances resource use and decision confidence: as soon as sufficient evidence

accumulates, one reaches a decision without wasting trials. This sequential QPing minimizes the expected number of entangled pairs consumed to reach a reliable accept/reject verdict. Explicit cost functions (e.g. expected number of pairs used as a function of true F and thresholds) could be derived using standard sequential hypothesis testing results [41]–[45].

Importantly, notice how a successful QPing diagnosis indirectly confirms the presence of an operational routing path between the end nodes, thereby validating both physical connectivity and entanglement feasibility.

Remark. This strategy suits well *heralded swapping* policies, i.e., policies where routers carry out swapping operations based on the swapping outcomes of other routers [32]. Since heralding already introduces sequential decision points, the path-based strategy can run alongside to confirm that the entire intended route is still entangled before committing to the task operations.

2) *Active Bouncing Strategy:*

- (i) *Path assumption.*– Given a path between two end nodes, choose a prior distribution $P(F(t))$ over fidelity values of the *two-way* path.
- (ii) *Collect data.*– A Bell pair is prepared locally and one half is sent through the quantum path and reflected back. Perform global operations (i.e., projection onto $|\Phi^+\rangle$) to gather statistics more efficiently [46].
- (iii) *Statistical update.*– From the data (e.g., k successful outcomes in n trials), update the posterior distribution over the *round-trip fidelity* $F_{rt}(t)$, defined as the effective fidelity after the round-trip transmission of the qubit, i.e. the fidelity of the qubit that has traversed the path twice. Since the strategy performs a round-trip transmission and measures global Bell-state projections, the probability of success per trial is given by the effective round-trip fidelity. For depolarizing channels it equals to:

$$P(F_{rt}) = F^2 + \frac{(1 - F)^2}{3}. \quad (6)$$

Then, using Bayes theorem Eq. (4), the posterior distribution $P(F_{rt}(t) | k, n)$ is computed.

- (iv) *Compute Posterior Probability.*– To test whether the original one-way channel is suitable, compare the inferred round-trip fidelity against the original target threshold F_0 . Specifically, compute:

$$P(F_{rt}(t) \geq F_0(t) | \text{data}) = \int_{F_0(t)}^1 P(F_{rt}(t) | \text{data}) dF,$$

with $F_0(t)$ being the operative threshold that takes into account the double use of the channel.

- (v) *Decision rule (hypothesis test).*– Choose a confidence threshold $\eta \in [0, 1]$.
 - If $P(F_{rt}(t) \geq F_0(t)) \geq \eta$, accept the link (ping success). Otherwise, reject the link (ping fail).

This bouncing strategy provides more powerful information per trial, but at the cost of increased noise as the path is used twice.

Bouncing Noise Factor. *In the bouncing QPing variant, a single qubit traverses each link twice. If each one-way channel is e.g. a depolarizing map of fidelity F , then the round-trip channel has fidelity*

$$F_{\text{rt}} \geq F^2, \quad (7)$$

which for a depolarizing channel equals $F_{\text{rt}} = F^2 + \frac{(1-F)^2}{3}$.

Consequently, to test against a target threshold F_0^T , one must use an operative threshold of $F_0 \geq F_0^{T^2}$ when interpreting bounce-based measurements (e.g., equaling $F_0 = F_0^{T^2} + \frac{(1-F_0^T)^2}{3}$ in the depolarizing case), up to time decay adjustments.

In both settings, QPing can be evaluated at different times, where the threshold fidelity is dynamically taken into account, considering the features discussed above. To make the active QPing strategy concrete, we consider a simple and representative instance. Each diagnostic trial produces a binary witness outcome, which we model as a Bernoulli random variable with some success probability, directly related to the effective end-to-end fidelity under a fixed noise model. As an example, we adopt a Beta prior $\text{Beta}(\alpha_0, \beta_0)$, with the uniform choice $\alpha_0 = \beta_0 = 1$ representing an agnostic setting. After each diagnostic outcome, the posterior is updated analytically via standard Beta–Binomial rules and compared against confidence thresholds to decide whether to accept, reject, or continue.

Notably, the prior distributions can be used to incorporate additional network knowledge, such as monitoring data or hardware characterization, without changing the structure of the protocol.

Operational Decision Rule. *Let $P(F)$ be the prior known distribution over end-to-end fidelity F , and let $F_0(t)$ be the current operative threshold at time t . Define*

$$P_1 = \int_{F_0(t)}^1 P(F) dF, \quad P_2 = 1 - P_1. \quad (8)$$

Given a confidence level $\eta \in (0, 1)$:

- If $P_1 \gg \eta$, it is concluded that the link is usable (skip QPing).
- If $P_2 \gg \eta$, it is concluded that the link is unusable (abort QPing).
- Otherwise, $P_2 < \eta < P_1$, the outcome is unclear (run QPing to resolve feasibility).

The above decision rule should be interpreted as an operational guideline for when to initiate, skip, or abort an active QPing procedure, rather than as a statistical statement about fidelity estimation. In practice, this decision rule is implemented together with a finite diagnostic budget (hit limit) on the number of entangled pairs consumed or elapsed time, as explicitly considered in Sec. V.

In both the end-node and bouncing versions of the active quantum ping, local twirling techniques [69], [70] may be applied to simplify noise models. In the bouncing strategy,

random Clifford twirling is feasible and transforms the effective channel into a depolarizing form, allowing for efficient fidelity witnessing via Bell measurements. In the end-node case, local Pauli twirling yields a Bell-diagonal state, simplifying the structure of the fidelity witnessing and improving statistical robustness, although full Clifford symmetrization is not implementable with local operations alone.

Remarkably, if the end nodes are able to store multiple entangled copies and perform collective operations on them, the efficiency of hypothesis testing can be exponentially improved [44], [46]. This enables an optimized strategy, in both end-node and bouncing strategies, for gathering the required statistics in the QPing protocol.

B. Segment-based Active QPing

The path-based QPing requires establishing full end-to-end connections solely to check the viability of a quantum link. However, in scenarios of highly loaded networks, this can be too demanding in terms of resources. We therefore explore an alternative strategy based on testing the individual segments that form the path between the end nodes, see Fig. 2 (b), based on the same strategies introduced above, i.e., making use of the end-node and bouncing approaches. The segment-based strategy tests individual path segments, either identified through the network routing functionality or determined by a link-level discovery process.

Composition Rule (Segment-based). *Consider a path of N segments, where segment i produces a Bell pair of fidelity F_i (depolarizing form) and each entanglement-swapping operation introduces a fixed fidelity factor q_{swap} . Under independent depolarizing noise on each link and ideal LOCC at the end nodes, the resulting end-to-end fidelity satisfies:*

$$F = \left(\prod_{i=1}^N F_i \right) q_{\text{swap}}^{N-1}, \quad (9)$$

up to time decay effects.

The above composition rule provides an idealized fidelity composition rule intended as a conceptual reference point rather than a deployable performance model. We assume heralded swaps, ideal local operations, and neglect temporal effects such as asynchronous link generation, swap failures, and memory decoherence during waiting times. These effects cannot be captured by a static multiplicative model and are therefore treated explicitly in the numerical, time-aware QPing analysis presented in Sec. V.

This method offers clear advantages in terms of reduced overhead and parallelizability, as all segments can be tested simultaneously. These features make the bouncing-based approach particularly viable in scenarios requiring rapid, parallel diagnostics over channels with relatively low noise. Its simplicity also facilitates deployment in near-term architectures. The steps for the segment-based ping strategy largely mirror those of the path-based ping, but are applied independently to each segment.

In cases where entanglement purification is available within individual segments, as in standard repeater settings [24]–[26], a key advantage is that the ping decision about the viability of establishing entanglement is not underestimated: it suffices to meet a threshold fidelity locally within each segment, rather than across the full end-to-end connection. This approach allows for a more modular and realistic assessment in various scenarios, such as high-loaded networks—where resource reservation for end-to-end connections might be strictly limited in time—or in cases where the path involves networks managed by different controllers. Although no global path is used in this strategy, successful certification across all segments effectively confirms that a route can be assembled via entanglement swapping.

Remark. The segment-based strategy suits unheralded swapping strategies, where each router performs the swapping independently and in parallel without awaiting the swapping outcomes of the others. The segment-based strategy can identify which segments are failing; furthermore, the results are useful for offline diagnostics to improve resource allocation in the next rounds.

However, this segmented approach might not capture the true performance of the entire end-to-end quantum channel. In particular, it neglects critical inter-node operations such as entanglement swapping, which may introduce nontrivial noise and failure that are invisible when testing links in isolation. To address this, length-two segments can be tested, including entanglement swapping operations at indeterminate nodes. This allows to determine the achievable fidelity for each segment, therefore deciding whether an entangled link, with or without entanglement purification at intermediate nodes, is viable.

This independence complicates the treatment of time, particularly when attempting to reconstruct the end-to-end entanglement generation performance. Since no actual end-to-end quantum state is created in this approach, one must instead extrapolate from individual segment metrics, while accounting for the expected behavior of entanglement swapping operations at intermediate nodes. Moreover, in case the bouncing approach is implemented, non-Markovian effects on the channel noise when bouncing back the particles could arise and affect the correct evaluation of the round-trip QPing. Importantly, additional delays introduced by swapping, along with potential decay in neighboring links that are ready earlier, must also be considered.

Both active QPing strategies can be combined and implemented on demand, suggesting that QPing should not be limited to a single test. Instead, it may consist of a suite of connectivity checks tailored to the network topology and capabilities. For instance, an end-to-end test based on entanglement distribution could be complemented by a segment-based test relying on local entanglement purification, both forming part of a more general and flexible QPing protocol.

Fig. 3: Resource-based quantum ping. Entanglement is already pre-shared between network constituents, and the ping protocol decides whether suitable (local) manipulation of the resource state can lead to direct and useful entanglement between end nodes.

C. Resource-based QPing

The last scenario considers the case where a shared entangled resource state has already been established among the network nodes, i.e., an entanglement-based quantum network [18], [21], and the end-to-end connection is achieved via local operations on this resource. In this situation, the task consists of determining, first, whether the two end nodes are part of the same entangled state, and second, whether they can be suitably connected through appropriate local manipulations, see Fig. 3.

Because identifying entanglement between specific parties within a large multipartite state is generally challenging [71], [72] without multipartite state characterization, we assume prior knowledge of the structure of the entangled resource $|\Psi_{res}\rangle$ and the protocol that ideally transforms it into the desired configuration. In particular, we consider that the network consistently generates a known entangled state during idle periods, allowing a predefined LOCC (local operations and classical communication) protocol to be used for establishing bipartite connections between selected nodes. For instance, if the resource state consists of a 1D cluster state, just applying Pauli Y measurements in the intermediate qubits and Pauli Z measurements on other neighbors achieves the desired end-to-end connection [73], [74]. Similar properties exist for more complex resource state structures, such as 2D cluster states [67], [75], [76].

Here, the fidelity ceases to be the most relevant figure of merit, since the goal is no longer to estimate how close a state is to a given target to, for instance, perform entanglement distillation, but rather to determine whether entanglement can be actually present. We therefore shift our focus to a more suitable quantity in this context: entanglement witnessing, although similar tools as before can be employed. The goal is to discern whether entanglement can be extracted between the end nodes, independently of local unitaries, for practical use. We can define resource-based quantum ping mode as follows.

TABLE I: Comparison of the different Quantum Ping strategies proposed

Active Path-Based QPing	
Time Sensitivity	Yes
Operations	Local or global (end-node or bouncing strategy)
Certification Method	Sequential hypothesis testing
Information per Trial	Medium (requires multiple rounds for confidence)
Robustness	Medium (whole path may be too sensitive to noise)
Active Segment-Based QPing	
Time Sensitivity	Partial (time per segment small, but global info indirect)
Operations	Local or global (and simultaneously for each segment)
Certification Method	Sequential hypothesis testing
Information per Trial	Low-medium (not directly end-to-end)
Robustness	High (no dependence on swapping or coordination)
Resource-Based QPing	
Time Sensitivity	Low (resource state pre-shared, conversion is quasi-immediate)
Operations	Local
Certification Method	Entanglement witnessing, Bell inequality
Information per Trial	High (if resource is high-quality, few pairs suffice)
Robustness	Low (require in general high quality entanglement)

Quantum Ping (Resource-based). *Determine whether two target nodes A and B , assumed to be part of a pre-shared entangled resource state $|\Psi_{\text{res}}\rangle$, can be locally transformed (for a given fixed LOCC) into a high-quality entangled state ρ_{AB} , and possibly verify the entanglement of ρ_{AB} .*

An important distinction in this scenario is that time evaluation is not as crucial, since high-quality entanglement is assumed to be pre-established during idle network functioning [18], [21]. Nodes may generate and store entangled links continuously, so that when a ping is issued, the entanglement is already available. This supports the possibility of reduced latency. Only local manipulation of the resource state is needed, which can be treated as quasi-timeless, although certain time considerations could need to be taken into account [76]. This can significantly reduce network idle times compared to schemes requiring repeated entanglement generation and coordination.

Remark. The resource-based QPing strategy operates in a conceptually different framework from active QPing modes. Rather than probing the feasibility of dynamically generating and distributing entanglement through physical channels, it assumes the existence of a pre-shared multipartite entangled resource and tests whether usable bipartite entanglement can be *extracted* from it by local operations. In this context, is associated with the structural properties of the underlying entangled resource. Specifically, let $|\Psi_{\text{res}}\rangle$ be a pre-shared graph-state resource on a network graph $G = (V, E)$. Two nodes $A, B \in V$ can extract a Bell pair by fixed LOCC if and only if there exists a path P from A to B in G . Equivalently, the localizable entanglement between A and B is nonzero precisely when G contains a connecting path.

This observation serves a structural prerequisite that drives

the design the resource-based QPing.

Accordingly, the goal is then to determine whether two end nodes can extract, via local operations, a usable bipartite entangled state. This approach does not rely on active path selection or channel establishment and is essentially unaffected by temporal constraints. After performing the local transformation to distill the bipartite state ρ_{AB} , the protocol verifies its entanglement either via fidelity witnessing [36], Bell-type inequalities violation [77], [78], or entanglement witnesses [79]–[81], depending on the expected quality of the output. Since almost no dynamical process is involved, the success criterion becomes less time-dependent and mainly structural.

The steps for the resource-based quantum ping strategy can be summarized as follows.

Resource-based Quantum Ping:

- (i) *Local procedure.*– Apply the known LOCC procedure to transform $|\Psi_{\text{res}}\rangle$ into a bipartite state between A and B .
- (ii) *Verify entanglement.*– Choose a witnessing strategy:
 - If ρ_{AB} is expected to be high-quality (either present or not): use binary entanglement witness or a Bell inequality test.
 - If possible low-quality entanglement is expected (e.g., some edges were faulty or missing): use fidelity witnessing based on sequential hypothesis testing as in the active ping scenario.
- (iii) *Collect data for the chosen witness strategy.*
- (iv) *Decision rule.*– Given the chosen witnessing strategy (up to confidence):
 - If using entanglement witness W : Check whether it satisfies $\text{Tr}[W\rho_{AB}] < 0$.
 - If using CHSH-like inequality: $|S| > 2$ implies entanglement.

- If using fidelity witnessing: Accept if $F \geq F_0$.

The choice of certification strategy depends strongly on the network setting, on the available prior knowledge, and on the desired confidence level for application. Bell inequality tests offer a device-independent route, but demand high experimental precision and a strong violation margin, typically requiring high-fidelity entangled states and detailed knowledge of the target expected states. Entanglement witnesses, on the other hand, can be very efficient in specific scenarios, particularly when the expected entangled state is well known, but it can also be partially state dependent. They can however fail to guarantee that there is no entanglement. Fidelity witnessing provides a balanced alternative: while not device-independent, it enables efficient, quantitative certification of entanglement with modest experimental overhead and is robust under noise, although it assumes knowledge of the target state.

Remark. With reference to the taxonomy provided in [32], the resource-based diagnostic mode naturally couples with proactive or virtual routing, where the external phase, i.e., generation of end-to-end connections, follows the path computation and leverages already established entangled links.

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In this section, we analyze the performance of the different QPing strategies introduced under different settings. The goal is a qualitative comparison, i.e., numerical values should be interpreted as indicative trends rather than hardware-specific predictions.

A. End-node vs. Bouncing Strategies

We first compare the end-node and bouncing realizations of QPing for a single elementary link. While the practical feasibility of bouncing is platform-dependent, it provides a useful understanding of the impact of increased information per diagnostic trial. Figure 4a shows the expected number of diagnostic trials required to reach a confident accept/reject decision as a function of the true channel fidelity F . For the bouncing strategy, the decision threshold is consistently mapped to the effective round-trip fidelity, such that both realizations diagnose the same underlying feature.

As expected, QPing reaches a decision rapidly when the channel is clearly usable or unusable, while the diagnostic cost increases sharply for fidelities close to the threshold F_0 . The bouncing realization can require fewer diagnostic trials in some regimes, also when accounting for channel uses, see Figure 4b, due to the additional information extracted per entangled pairs consumed when both qubits are jointly measured. However, the additional round-trip loss penalizes performance near the threshold, highlighting a tradeoff between information gain and robustness.

Importantly, QPing does not aim to minimize worst-case diagnostic cost, but rather to enable early termination in clearly infeasible regimes, thereby avoiding the substantially higher cost of other benchmarking tools or executing applications on unusable links. While QPing may incur non-negligible

diagnostic cost near the operative threshold, this behavior is unavoidable for any statistically sound test and is precisely the regime where early abort decisions are most valuable.

B. Path vs. Segment Strategies

Figure 5 compares segment-based and path-based QPing strategies in a repeater chain setting with probabilistic and time-consuming entanglement generation, entanglement swapping, and memory decoherence. The two strategies differ fundamentally in what they diagnose. The segment-based approach tests each elementary link simultaneously and independently and accepts a route whenever all links satisfy segment thresholds derived from multiplicative composition. Importantly, the protocol stops whenever any segment rejects. By construction, this strategy is blind to swap imperfections and waiting-time-induced decoherence. In contrast, the path-based strategy operates on actually delivered end-to-end entangled states and therefore captures the full temporal and operational cost of the entanglement distribution.

In this comparison, the path-based strategy serves as a reference diagnostic, as it directly probes the fidelity of the end-to-end entangled state actually delivered under some network dynamics. Disagreement events therefore correspond to optimistic errors of the segment-based strategy, where local link tests suggest usability but end-to-end entanglement cannot be established above the operative threshold. To avoid arbitrarily long diagnostic runs near the operative threshold, the sequential test is capped at a maximum number of samples (“hit limit” N_{\max}), and runs that reach this limit without reaching a confident decision are treated as inconclusive and assigned a maximum cost.

As shown in Fig. 5a, both strategies yield comparable acceptance probabilities for short paths. However, as the path length increases, the probability of disagreement, i.e., where the segment-based strategy accepts while the path-based strategy rejects, grows. This highlights the fundamental limitation of local diagnostics that high-quality elementary links do not necessarily imply usable end-to-end entanglement under realistic network dynamics.

Figure 5b reports the expected time to reach a route-level decision. As expected, the segment-based strategy typically reaches a decision faster, due to parallel local diagnostics and the absence of global coordination overhead. The path-based strategy incurs significantly larger latencies due to asynchronous link generation, repeated swap attempts, and decoherence during the preparation time. For large L , the expected path-based decision time decreases again, as the route becomes very likely to be rejected early due to decoherence or swap failure, leading to rapid termination of the diagnostic process.

Times are expressed in normalized units relative to the duration of an elementary entanglement-generation attempt. The results are platform-agnostic, should be interpreted qualitatively, and can be rescaled to concrete hardware parameters.

(a) Expected diagnostic cost of QPing as a function of the true single channel fidelity F for end-node and bouncing realizations.

(b) Expected number of channel uses under same conditions of Fig. 4a.

Fig. 4: End-node vs. bouncing QPing strategies. Expected number of diagnostic samples $E[N]$ versus true single-pass fidelity F for confidence levels $\eta \in \{0.95, 0.99\}$ under a depolarizing noise model with operative threshold $F_0 = 0.85$. The sequential Bayesian test is capped by a hit limit $N_{\max} = 3000$ samples; runs that do not reach an accept/reject decision within N_{\max} are declared inconclusive and assigned cost N_{\max} . Results are obtained via Monte Carlo sampling with $R = 3000$ independent runs per F .

C. Time-dependent Feasibility Analysis

Figure 6 analyzes the feasibility of path-based QPing in the presence of time-dependent decoherence. The figure reports the probability that QPing reaches a confident *accept* decision before the effective end-to-end fidelity decays below the operative threshold F_0 , as a function of the entanglement generation success probability p_{gen} and the memory coherence time τ . We model memory decoherence using a generic exponential decay $F(t) = F(t_0)e^{-t/\tau}$, where τ is an effective coherence time and t is the elapsed preparation time of the end-to-end state. The elapsed time explicitly includes entanglement generation attempts, probabilistic entanglement swapping, and diagnostic measurements along the route. Classical communication delays and hardware-specific latencies are absorbed into the same normalized time units.

The figure should be interpreted as a feasibility phase diagram. For low p_{gen} or short memory lifetimes, QPing almost always expires before sufficient statistical evidence can be accumulated, resulting in a near-zero acceptance probability. In contrast, when entanglement generation is reliable and memory coherence times are long compared to the diagnostic latency, QPing succeeds with high probability. The sharp transition between these regimes defines a feasibility boundary that cannot be inferred from static fidelity considerations alone.

This behavior arises from the interplay between probabilistic entanglement generation, sequential entanglement swapping, and decoherence during the entanglement preparation time. Even when the initial end-to-end fidelity exceeds the operative threshold, diagnostics may become infeasible if the time required to gather evidence is comparable to the memory lifetime. Overall, Fig. 6 provides an operational criterion for when active, path-based QPing should be executed and when

it should be skipped or aborted.

D. Resource-based Scenario

A key distinguishing feature of the resource-based diagnostic mode is its immediacy in time. Resource states are assumed to be pre-distributed during idle periods or background operation of the network, such that diagnostic verification can be performed quasi-instantaneously when needed. In this regime, the diagnostic latency is dominated by a small, fixed number of local measurements and classical post-processing, and is therefore largely independent of path length or network dynamics.

This immediacy comes at the cost of flexibility: the diagnostic outcome reflects only the quality of the pre-shared resource state at the time of verification and cannot adapt to time-varying noise, probabilistic swapping, or transient failures. As a result, resource-based diagnostics provide a fast but coarse connectivity, while active QPing protocols trade latency for adaptivity and statistical robustness under realistic network operation, see also table I. A direct quantitative comparison between these protocols is therefore not meaningful, as they certify fundamentally different operational properties under incompatible assumptions.

VI. OUTLOOK AND CONCLUSIONS

We have introduced the concept of a *Quantum Ping* (QPing) protocol as a diagnostic primitive tool for quantum networks. Drawing inspiration from its classical analogue, the QPing aims to probe connectivity between two quantum network nodes, understood here as the capacity to establish useful entanglement, using minimal resources and with operational relevance for future quantum networks. This tool can complement entanglement routing by providing dynamic and efficient

(a) Acceptance probability of the segment-based strategy, the path-based strategy, and the probability of disagreement (segment accepts while path rejects)

(b) Expected time to reach a route level decision.

Fig. 5: Comparison between segment-based and path-based QPing strategies as a function of the number of segments L . Results are obtained via Monte Carlo sampling for an end-to-end operative threshold $F_0 = 0.8$ and confidence level $\eta = 0.97$, assuming depolarizing noise, probabilistic entanglement generation with success probability $p_{\text{gen}} = 0.5$, entanglement swapping with success probability $p_{\text{swap}} = 0.5$ and fidelity factor $q_{\text{swap}} = 0.98$, and exponential memory decoherence with coherence time $\tau = 10$ (normalized units). A uniform prior probability distribution is assumed for the sequential decision process.

Fig. 6: Feasibility of active, path-based QPing under time-dependent decoherence. The color scale shows the probability that QPing reaches a confident accept decision before the effective end-to-end fidelity decays below the operative threshold F_0 , as a function of the entanglement generation success probability p_{gen} and the memory coherence time τ . Results correspond to a linear repeater chain of length $L = 3$ with per-link fidelity $F_{\text{seg}} = 0.99$, swap fidelity $q_{\text{swap}} = 0.99$, swap success probability $p_{\text{swap}} = 0.9$, and operative threshold $F_0 = 0.85$. A uniform prior probability distribution is assumed for the sequential decision process.

connectivity information to support path discovery and routing decisions, thereby enhancing quantum network robustness and scalability. From this perspective, QPing can be seen as a pre-screening tool for quantum network Quality of Service (QoS): by comparing current network performance indicators against

time-dependent thresholds, one can decide whether attempting entanglement is worthwhile or whether performance upgrades are required.

We propose several realizations of the quantum ping protocol, each considering different architectural constraints and resource assumptions. These include (i) an *active path-based* strategy where entanglement is established dynamically across an entire path and verified using local or global witnessing methods; (ii) a *active segment-based* variant where individual segments are benchmarked simultaneously and independently; and (iii) a *resource-based strategy* in which pre-shared entangled resource states are manipulated locally to extract and certify bipartite entanglement between the target nodes. While each of these scenarios is meant for particular settings, realistic networks may require hybrid schemes. For example, if two nodes are not directly connected in a graph-state resource, one might perform local measurements to route entanglement through intermediate nodes. Exploring such semi-active pings, is a promising direction for future work.

A practical implementation of QPing also necessitates a robust classical control plane. The iterative nature of the diagnostic requires the exchange of classical measurement outcomes and decision triggers between the nodes. In high-rate networks or scenarios with significant classical propagation delay, this coordination introduces a non-negligible latency overhead. While this work prioritizes the optimization of scarce quantum resources (e.g., entangled pairs and memory coherence), minimizing classical coordination overheads remains a critical objective for future protocol refinement.

Further directions also include studying quantum ping in dynamic and realistic settings, where topology or noise levels change over time, and extending the framework to multipartite

scenarios, while integrating the tool within quantum networks protocol stack. Beyond specific implementations, the QPing abstraction provides a conceptual bridge between lower-layer entanglement-based protocol performance and higher-layer utilization and control, enabling resource-efficient entanglement diagnostics.

In a similar direction, integrating QPing into a standard sequential hypothesis-testing framework would offer several benefits: it would enable rigorous control of error rates, yield explicit bounds on the required number of diagnostic trials, and facilitate incorporation of well-established results from the classical sequential-analysis literature.

Additionally, one could also consider ping strategies in device-independent or semi-device-independent regimes, where assumptions on the trustworthiness of measurements are relaxed. Another relevant line would be to explore how ping strategies can be integrated into entanglement routing algorithms, with real-time diagnostics feeding back into path selection or entanglement scheduling.

Beyond its standalone diagnostic role, QPing strategies can naturally be interpreted as a *service-level unit* within more complex quantum network architectures. In such settings, QPing outcomes can be consumed by higher-layer entities responsible for scheduling, resource allocation, and contention management, providing timely and quantitative information on the feasibility of establishing entanglement between candidate node pairs. This allows QPing to be extended and orchestrated to support concurrent requests and dynamic network conditions, without embedding architecture-specific control logic into the primitive itself.

As a final remark, it is worthwhile to clarify that QPing strategies do not aim to substitute the classical ping program, which is a prerequisite for quantum networks as well, but to extend its utility to quantum connectivity. Indeed, quantum ping primitives provide a simple but powerful tool to dynamically certify entanglement-based connectivity in realistic quantum networks. We expect it to play a central role in the operational stack of future quantum communication architectures.

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